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Stark

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(54) **REDUCING FIBER CROSSTALK IN MINERAL OPTICAL FIBER ARRAYS**

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(*) Notice: Subject to any disclaimer, the term of this patent is extended or adjusted under 35 U.S.C. 154(b) by 0 days.

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(52) **U.S. Cl.**
CPC **G02B 6/06** (2013.01); **G02B 27/0025** (2013.01)

(57) **ABSTRACT**

(58) **Field of Classification Search**
CPC G02B 6/06
See application file for complete search history.

This invention is an optical improvement to minerals that exhibit an image translation capability. These minerals translate an image between faces; however, the minerals exhibit considerable crosstalk between crystal fibers, which reduce image sharpness, contrast, and signal. This invention greatly reduces crystal fiber crosstalk.

4 Claims, 5 Drawing Sheets

